

DECODE: Delirium Detection from Continuous Digital Behaviour in Dementia

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Abstract. Delirium is a frequent and serious complication in people with dementia, often precipitated by infections or physiological instability. It is associated with accelerated cognitive decline, increased hospital admissions, and elevated mortality. Despite its clinical importance, delirium is often underdiagnosed in community and care home settings, where early signs may be missed. This study leverages passively collected behavioural and physiological data from the Technology Integrated Health Management (TIHM) project to develop an AI-based model for early delirium detection. We integrated digital markers including sleep-wake cycle disruption and agitation, validated proxies for delirium, into a personalised predictive framework. Sleep bout count, average bout duration, and daytime activity count were derived as indicators of circadian rhythm. Preliminary analysis suggests that circadian disruption may precede agitation episodes. We are currently integrating these features into a unified machine learning framework to predict early delirium risk. Our findings highlight the promise of intelligent monitoring systems in enabling earlier intervention and supporting proactive dementia care.

Keywords: Delirium, Machine learning, Digital markers, Early detection, Intelligent healthcare

1 Introduction

Delirium is a neuropsychiatric syndrome characterized by acute and fluctuating disturbances in attention, cognition, and arousal. It is particularly prevalent among people living with dementia, with incidence rates ranging from 20–60% depending on the setting. Delirium in dementia is associated with a faster rate of cognitive decline, increased institutionalization, longer hospital stays, and significantly elevated mortality. Despite these risks, delirium often remains undetected in home or care home environments, especially during its early stages.

Current detection relies heavily on clinical evaluation using tools such as the Confusion Assessment Method (CAM) [1], which require face-to-face assessment and are rarely applied outside acute care settings. In recent years, there has been increasing interest in using digital health technologies and passive monitoring to identify early warning signs of clinical deterioration in dementia. The Technology Integrated Health Management (TIHM) project [2] offers a unique opportunity to explore this approach, having collected continuous behavioural and

physiological data from people living with dementia using smart home devices.

This study presents the DECODE framework, which aims to detect early signs of delirium in dementia through digital proxies including agitation, sleep-wake cycle disturbance, and its common trigger-infection. By developing machine learning models trained in real-world, passively collected data, we aim to enable earlier recognition of delirium risk and support timely intervention in community and residential settings.

2 Methods

2.1 TIHM Dataset and Proxy Markers for Delirium

We used data from the TIHM for Dementia project, a real-world digital monitoring initiative that enrolled individuals with a confirmed diagnosis of dementia or mild cognitive impairment living at home [2]. For this analysis, we included this dataset of 56 participants who had 8 to 20 consecutive weeks of valid monitoring data.

Given the absence of a clinical delirium diagnosis in the dataset, we defined digital proxies for delirium based on established clinical criteria (e.g., CAM) and prior literature: **A.** Sleep-wake cycle disruption, computed using: Total sleep duration, Number of sleep bouts per night, Average sleep bout length, Daytime activity count. Sleep quality, computed as the sum or mean of scores assigned to each sleep bout during the night, based on the scoring algorithm defined in a previous study [3]. **B.** Sleep regularity/irregularity, measured as the cosine similarity or Euclidean distance between the current day's hourly sleep duration percentage pattern and that of the preceding 5 days. **C.** Agitation episodes, derived from labelled data validated against clinical observation.

These features were organized into time-series structures to capture temporal dynamics preceding proxy-defined delirium events.

2.2 Feature Engineering and Modeling

We implemented a multi-stage pipeline for sleep anomaly detection: **A.** Sleep cycle disturbances were visually plotted using the durations of each sleep state (including wake, light, deep, and REM) for each day (see results Fig. 1 for illustration). Further quantification of sleep cycle disturbances will be performed by weighing various measures, including the number of sleep bouts and durations. **B.** Isolation Forest was used to detect anomalies using multiple variables, including seven physiological measures and the activity entropy rate. **C.** Outliers in sleep duration were flagged directly when the sleep duration exceeded a threshold of three times the median absolute deviation.

3. Results

3.1 Sleep Disruption and Agitation Proxy Events

Fig. 1. Representative sleep patterns around agitation (red dashed line).

Figure 1 illustrates representative sleep patterns surrounding agitation episodes. On 11/05/2019, an agitation event was preceded by excessive daytime sleep and fragmented nighttime rest. In contrast, the 14/05/2019 event was preceded by prolonged wakefulness the night before.

Fig. 2. Correlation between agitation episode numbers and four sleep scores: Including sleep quality (sum and mean scores) and sleep regularity/irregularity (based on 5-day cosine similarity and Euclidean distance).

Figure 2 demonstrates that, except for the sleep quality sum score, all other measures, including the sleep quality mean score and the two similarity measures reflecting sleep pattern regularity—are correlated with the number of agitation episodes, with correlations above 0.1. These results provide indirect evidence supporting the validity of our derived sleep scores.

3.2 Multimodal Anomaly Detection

We further visualised overlapping sleep duration anomalies with physiological and activity deviations using multivariate isolation. Figure 3 displays how integrated digital markers captured disturbances preceding agitation episodes.

Fig.3. Representative Sleep anomalies (purple dashed line) and multimodal anomalies using multivariate forest isolation based on physiological data and entropy rate.

4. Future Directions

The DECODE framework integrates behavioral and physiological markers to generate individualised risk predictions. Future work will focus on generating a comprehensive delirium risk score and including common infections into the algorithm. It will be necessary to validate these findings externally, refining predictive thresholds, and integrating outputs into clinical decision-support tools for community-based dementia care.

References

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